

Erotylid sp. nov. MS4
Cycad fungus beetle

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Insect

Size: 6-7 mm in length

Distribution:

Eastern Cape near Kariega and Gqeberha

Importance:

These beetles form part of a complex that pollinates highly endangered cycads in South Africa. The sequencing will contribute to understanding the diversity of beetles and host relationships to inform conservation and pollinator recovery plans

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 29.1 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 5.51 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.89 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.7% [Single: 91.7%, Duplicated: 8.0%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 10 799 kilobases

Contig number: 531

Sample Contributor contact details:

Professor John Donaldson

Wild Cycad Conservancy; University of Pretoria

JD@cycads2050.org

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